

SIP Ingestion Protocol - Archivist's Guide

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1. Purpose of this guide

This guide is intended for archivists tasked with preparing and validating Submission Information Packages (SIPs) in compliance with the e-ARK specifications. It outlines best practices, mandatory steps, and validation procedures to ensure a reliable and structured ingestion workflow.

2. Standards and software in use

E-ARK

The E-ARK project was a multinational European initiative aimed at improving digital archiving practices across member states. It resulted in the development of standardized specifications for structuring information packages, now maintained by the DILCIS Board (Digital Information LifeCycle Interoperability Standards Board). These specifications build on the OAIS reference model (ISO 14721), particularly its concept of information packages, to provide practical guidance for digital preservation workflows.

Figure 1: E-ARK SIP folder structure

METS (Metadata Encoding and Transmission Standard)

METS is a core component of the E-ARK information package model. It serves as a container for linking together descriptive, administrative, structural, and preservation metadata. Within

an E-ARK SIP, METS provides the formal XML framework used to organize and reference the different parts of the package, such as the metadata files, data files, and their relationships. METS acts as the backbone of the package, ensuring coherence and interoperability across archiving systems.

The protocol uses METS 1.x, as defined by the Common Specification for Information Packages (CSIP), and follows the official XSD schemas provided by the DILCIS Board.

PREMIS (Preservation Metadata Implementation Strategy)

PREMIS is the international standard for encoding preservation metadata and plays a critical role in supporting long-term access to digital content. In the context of E-ARK, PREMIS is used to document technical details, preservation actions (events), responsible agents, and rights associated with digital objects. It helps ensure that digital materials remain understandable, authentic, and usable over time.

This protocol uses PREMIS 3.0, with XML metadata directly linked from the METS file (via amdSec/digiprovMD). PREMIS metadata is especially important for maintaining integrity, recording fixity information (e.g., SHA-256 checksums), and tracking preservation workflows. Although technically optional in E-ARK SIPs, it is essential for digital preservation compliance and tool interoperability.

EAD (Encoded Archival Description)

EAD is the standard used to encode hierarchical descriptive metadata for archival collections. In the E-ARK SIP framework, EAD is used to provide intellectual context and detailed content description, often structured according to archival levels such as fonds, series, files, and items.

The protocol produces EAD version 3 (ead.xml) from a structured Excel form filled in by the archivist. The EAD file is referenced in the METS dmdSec and ensures compatibility with international archival systems and discovery platforms.

FITS (File Information Tool Set)

FITS (File Information Tool Set) is a Java-based software utility developed by Harvard University to identify, validate, and extract technical metadata from digital files. Within the E-ARK SIP workflow, FITS 1.6.0 is used to analyze each file and produce a unified XML output that aggregates results from multiple embedded tools. This output provides detailed format identification, file properties, and checksums, which are later incorporated into PREMIS metadata for preservation purposes.

The following tools are included in the FITS configuration:

- DROID: For file format identification using PRONOM signatures (UK National Archives).
- JHOVE: For validation of digital formats (e.g., PDF, TIFF).
- ExifTool: For extraction of embedded metadata (e.g., camera, GPS, author).
- Apache Tika: For content and metadata extraction.
- NLNZ Metadata Extractor: Specialized for preservation use cases.

- FFident: Format recognition tool.
- File Utility: UNIX-based file type detection.

By default, FITS generates MD5 checksums, but the protocol overrides this with SHA-256 hashes, which are computed using Python’s hashlib library. This substitution ensures stronger fixity control, as SHA-256 is cryptographically more secure and aligned with current digital preservation standards.

FITS outputs are then parsed and selectively integrated into PREMIS metadata, particularly in the form of file-level technical characteristics and significant properties.

3. Protocol architecture

Figure 2: Ingest protocol

The protocol (illustrated in Figure 2) is initiated by the Producer, who consults the Guideline “How to prepare and transfer your data to the Records and Archives Service” to learn how to properly structure their data before transfer, and then submits their files along with the Archival Transfer of Custody (ATOC) form. The Archivist checks the data and launches the script **A-Description_Form.py**, which automatically generates a pre-filled description form with fields such as creation dates or file names. Manual fields (description, rights, restrictions, etc.) are then completed by the archivist.

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Figure 3: Detailed process of SIP Builder tool

Next, the script `B-SIP_Builder.py` (as in Figure 3) orchestrates the complete construction of the SIP. The process starts with the script `1-Item_List_Creation.py`, which generates a complete list of files found in the source folder. It also identifies, for information purposes only, files with formats not compliant with accepted extensions, without applying any corrective treatment.

The script `2-StructureEARK_Creation.py` then creates a SIP structure in which the files are copied following the required organization (representation directories, metadata, schemas, documentation).

The script `3-MD_Creation.py` uses the archival description form to generate an `ead.xml` file structuring the descriptive metadata of the SIP.

The script `4-FITS_Starter.py` runs file analysis via the FITS tool, generates SHA-256 checksums, and produces a consolidated file containing the analysis results (`*_fits_global.xml`). The following scripts use these results to construct the other SIP components.

The scripts `5-METS_Rep.py` and `6-PREMIS_Rep.py` rely on the FITS results and the description form to generate, for each representation, the METS and PREMIS files respectively.

The scripts `7-METS_Root.py` and `8-PREMIS_Root.py` perform the same operations at the root level of the package, to document the SIP as a whole.

The script `9-MD_Updater.py` updates the various metadata files to establish necessary links between objects, descriptive files, preservation files, and representations.

The script `10-Validator_Schemas.py` performs XML validation of all generated files against their respective XSD schemas, ensuring the syntactic compliance of the SIP.

Finally, the script `11-IntegrityCheck.py` verifies the integrity of the package: it checks for consistency between expected and actual files and validates the SHA-256 checksums recorded in the PREMIS files, thereby confirming the authenticity of the digital objects.

4. Tool structure

The SIP Builder tool is structured into several directories and files at the root of the project.

- `src/`: Contains all modular Python scripts that handle the different steps of the ingestion protocol: SIP creation, metadata generation, technical analysis, file validation, etc. There is no need to modify this folder and its files.
- `schemas/`: Includes XSD files used to validate the generated XML files. There is no need to modify this folder and its files.
- `workspace/`: Serves as a temporary working area where intermediate files are stored, such as: the Description Form, the Archival Transfer of Custody, or the FITS output file.

Two main scripts are available at the root level:

- `A-Description_Form.py`: Automatically generates a description form based on a structured directory.
- `B-SIP_Builder.py`: Orchestrates the complete SIP building process by calling the internal modules in sequence.

The `requirements.txt` file lists all necessary Python dependencies, which must be installed via pip before launching the tool.

5. Information encoded in metadata

EAD

At the fonds level (root `<archdesc>`), the following information can be recorded:

- Fonds title (Title)
- Reference code
- Coverage dates (Coverage from, Coverage to)
- Language(s)
- Scope and content
- Information security level

At the component level (`<c>` nodes) for each hierarchical level:

- Title
- Alternative title
- Reference code and symbols
- Coverage dates (Coverage from, Coverage to)
- Document date

- Scope and content
- Notes
- Custodial history
- Archivist’s notes
- Related units of description
- Creator
- Recipient
- GATT/NGO Bodies
- Document type
- Subject
- Mentioned countries
- Medium
- Language(s)
- Access and use rights (Information Security, Rights, Disclosure Circular)
- DAO (Digital Object References) to: alternate files, copies, locations, and stored file paths

METS

The header (<metsHdr>) contains the following:

- Creation date (CREATEDATE)
- Document status (RECORDSTATUS)
- Agents (multiple):
 - Software (name and version)
 - Archivist (organization and identifier)
 - Producer (name and identifier)
 - Preservation agent (organization and identifier)

The descriptive section (<dmdSec>) references the ead.xml file, including:

- Metadata type (EAD version 3)
- SHA-256 checksum
- File size
- Creation date
- Relative path

The administrative section (<amdSec>) has two parts:

- rightsMD: extracted from the “Rights” field of the description form, in XML format
- digiprovMD: references the corresponding PREMIS file

The file section (<fileSec>) structure differs depending on whether it’s the root METS or a representation METS. In the root METS file, files are grouped into <fileGrp> blocks according to their purpose:

- USE="schemas": contains the XSD schemas used for XML validation
- USE="documentation": includes support documents such as the Transfer of Custody and the description form

In the representation METS files, each digital file in the data/ folder is individually described in a <file> element with:

- Unique ID (@ID): an auto-generated UUID
- MIME type (@MIMETYPE): e.g., application/pdf, identified via FITS
- File size (@SIZE)
- SHA-256 checksum (@CHECKSUM): to ensure integrity
- Creation date (@CREATED): if available from FITS
- Logical SIP path (<FLocat href=“...”>): reflecting the folder structure

These are grouped under <fileGrp USE=“representation/data”>.

The physical structure (<structMap>) also differs between root and representation METS. In the root METS, the structure is divided into several logical directories, each represented by a <div>:

- metadata: contains a descriptive subset pointing to ead.xml
- representations: links each representation via <mptr> to its respective METS file (representations/repX/METS.xml)
- schemas: groups the XSD files
- documentation: contains support documents

In representation METS, the structure reflects the internal organization of each representation:

- A metadata directory contains the PREMIS file for the representation
- A data directory mirrors the folder/subfolder structure

Each file is represented by a <div TYPE=“Item”> element, associated with an ID via a pointer (<fptr>), which refers to the detailed file definition in <fileSec>.

PREMIS

At the root PREMIS level, the following are recorded:

- SIP identifier (UUID)
- UUIDs of each representation
- Ingestion event:
 - Event type: ingestion
 - Date and time
 - Outcome: successful
 - Link to the associated SIP object
- Involved agents:
 - Individuals (e.g., producer)
 - Organizations (e.g., archives service)
 - Software tools (e.g., FITS, SIP Builder), with name, version, and role
- Rights:
 - Rights identifier (UUID)
 - Legal basis (e.g., Copyright)
 - Generic license note

In representation PREMIS files, the following information differs:

- Digital objects (<object type="file">):
 - UUID
 - Original name
 - Storage path
 - File size
 - MIME format
 - SHA-256 checksum (with algorithm and origin)
 - Technical properties extracted from FITS
 - Link to the representation containing the file
- Relations:
 - Each file is linked to its representation
 - A dependency is recorded if a software tool is required to interpret the file
- Environmental objects (<object type="intellectualEntity">):
 - Tools/software used to create or process the files
 - Name, version, type, and function
- Processing events:
 - Format identification
 - Validation (well-formed, valid)
 - Date, outcome, involved agents
 - Explicitly linked to each relevant file
- Software agents:
 - All tools identified as active via FITS
 - Includes SIP Builder
 - For each agent: name, version, type, role note, and link to the rights block
- Rights block (<rights>):
 - Rights identifier (UUID)
 - Legal basis: "other"
 - Rights documentation (from the “Rights” field of the form)
 - Link to this rights block from each software agent

6. Allowed file formats

The file formats allowed may be changed at the beginning of the script `1-ItemList_Creation.py`.

Format	Status	Comments
Text		
PDF/A	Preferred	ISO standard for long-term preservation (PDF/A-1, A-2, A-3). Supports metadata, stable.
PDF	Accepted	Common format; should be migrated to PDF/A when possible.
ODT	Preferred	Open ISO-standard format, XML-based, good interoperability.
DOCX	Accepted	XML-based, widely supported, but proprietary (Microsoft).

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TXT	Accepted	Universal plain text format; only preserves text content.
Spreadsheets		
CSV	Preferred	Readable, simple, interoperable; no formatting or formulas.
ODS	Preferred	Open ISO-standard format, XML-based, good interoperability.
XLSX	Accepted	XML-based, widely supported, but proprietary (Microsoft).
Presentations		
ODP	Preferred	Open ISO-standard format, XML-based, good interoperability.
PPTX	Accepted	XML-based, widely supported, but proprietary (Microsoft).
PDF/A	Accepted	ISO standard for long-term preservation; only static content supported.
Databases		
SQLITE	Preferred	Lightweight, open, single-file format for relational databases.
DB	Preferred	Lightweight, open, single-file format for relational databases.
CSV	Accepted	Readable and interoperable; lacks relational structure.
SIARD	Accepted	Standardized, open format for relational archiving; maintained by the Swiss Federal Archives.
Images		
JPEG2000	Preferred	Lossless or lossy compression; good for preservation, but less common.
TIFF	Preferred	Lossless, stable format with metadata support (EXIF, XMP).
JPEG	Accepted	Lossy compression; acceptable if no higher-quality version exists.
PNG	Accepted	Lossless, suited for web images and diagrams; less ideal for high-res photography.
Audio		
WAV	Preferred	Uncompressed, highly stable; preservation standard.
FLAC	Preferred	Lossless compression, embedded metadata; excellent for archiving.
BWF	Preferred	Standardized WAV variant, uncompressed, supports metadata.
MP3	Accepted	Lossy compression; widely used, less suited for preservation.
Video		
MKV (FFV1)	Preferred	Lossless encoding, open container; ideal for preservation.
AVI	Preferred	Uncompressed format; large but stable.
MP4	Accepted	Common format; uses lossy compression.
Email		
EML	Preferred	Open format, readable in multiple email clients.
MBOX	Preferred	Standard format for archiving entire mailboxes.
MSG	Accepted	Proprietary Microsoft format.
PST	Accepted	Proprietary Microsoft format.

PDF/A	Preferred	ISO format for long-term preservation (PDF/A-1, A-2, A-3). Supports metadata, stable.
EA-PDF	TBD	Promising format based on PDF/A, but very recent.

7. Installation of FITS and SIP Builder tool

First, ensure that Java (minimum JDK 8) is installed on the machine. You can verify its presence by running the `java -version` command in the terminal.

Next, download the latest version of FITS from the project’s release page: <https://github.com/harvard-lts/fits/releases>, selecting the archive named `fits-1.6.0.zip`. Extract the folder to the desired installation location.

To improve accessibility of the program, you can add the `fits.bat` file to the system PATH on Windows.

In the script `4-FITS_Starter.py`, you must adapt the `fits_home` variable on line 168 by specifying the absolute path to the installed FITS folder.

Python 3.9 or higher must be installed and accessible via terminal/command prompt. Before launching the application, make sure to install all required Python dependencies. These are listed in the `requirements.txt` file located at the root of the project. To install them, open a terminal, navigate to the project folder, and run the following command:

```
pip install -r requirements.txt
```

8. SIP Builder tool: steps

1. Preparing the Source Folder

- Organize the source data in a hierarchical structure: Fonds > Sub-fonds > Group of series > Series > File > Document (which is referred as Item). The hierarchy may begin at any of these levels, depending on the archival context.
- Each *file* (in the archival hierarchy sense of the term) will become one *representation* in the SIP.
- Do not skip levels in the hierarchy.
- Avoid identical names for folders and individual documents (e.g., do not name both a file and an item "Report 2023").

Example directories

```

Producer_SIP_001/
  serie1/
    file1/
      document1.pdf
    file2/
      document2.pdf

```

```

Producer_SIP_001/
  groupofseries1/
    serie1/
      file1/
        photo1.tiff
    serie2/
      file2/
        document2.pdf
  groupofseries2/
  etc.

```

2. Generating the Description Form

Run the script `A-DescriptionForm.py` to generate the Excel description form, which will be saved in the `/workspace` folder as `DescriptionForm_[SIPname].xlsx`. When prompted, specify the starting level of your folder structure.

For instance, if your top-level folders represent series (as shown in the first example above), type “series”. If they represent groups of series (as in the second example), type “group of series”.

3. Completing the Description Form

Open the `DescriptionForm_[SIPname].xlsx` in the `/workspace` folder. Some fields may be already automatically filled out.

Required Fields

- Title
- Level of description (must be one of: fonds, subfonds, group of series, series, file, item)
- All applicable hierarchy columns (Fonds, Sub-fonds, Group of series, Series, File)
- Storage location (relative folder path for items)

Hierarchy consistency

- Start at the appropriate level: If your directory structure begins at “Group of series”, you must manually insert rows for the missing superior levels, namely “Sub-fonds” and “Fonds”. These additional rows must be explicitly filled in, as they are not generated automatically. All other rows will have their hierarchy columns auto completed based on the folder structure.
- No skipped levels: Ensure all parent levels are present and filled consistently in the corresponding columns.
- Avoid duplicate names between hierarchy levels.

Example entry

Title	Level of description	File	Series	Group of series	Subfonds	Fonds
NGO Archives	fonds					
Legal Affairs Division	subfonds					NGO Archives
Agreements	group of series				Legal Affairs Division	NGO Archives
LFM Documents	series			Agreements	Legal Affairs Division	NGO Archives
Uruguay Round Folder	file		LFM Documents	Agreements	Legal Affairs Division	NGO Archives
DraftAgreement 2993	item	Uruguay Round Folder	LFM Documents	Agreements	Legal Affairs Division	NGO Archives

4. Running the SIP Builder

Run the script `B-SIPBuilder.py` from the root of your working directory. This script automates the entire SIP generation process.

Before processing begins, you will be prompted to enter three values:

- Producer name (e.g., "NGO Legal Division")
- Producer identifier (e.g., "NGO-LEG")
- SIP rights statement (free-text field, e.g., "Internal use only")

Steps performed automatically

- `1-ItemList_Creation.py`: Scans the source directory and generates `FileList.csv` and if needed `NonCompliantFiles.csv`.
- `2-StructureEARK_Creation.py`: Builds the e-ARK folder structure.
- `3-MD_Creation.py`: Generates the `ead.xml` metadata from the Description Form.
- `4-FITS_Starter.py`: Runs FITS, analyzes all files and creates `[SIPname]_fits_global.xml`.
- `5-METS_Rep.py`: Generates `METS.xml` for each representation.
- `6-PREMIS_Rep.py`: Generates `[repX]_PREMIS.xml` for each representation.
- `7-METS_Root.py`: Generate the `METS.xml` at the root level.
- `8-PREMIS_Root.py`: Generates the `PREMIS.xml` at the root level.
- `9-MD_Updater.py`: Inserts PREMIS and rights info into METS and PREMIS files.
- `10-Validator_Schemas.py`: Checks all XMLs against XSD schemas.
- `11-IntegrityCheck.py`: Verifies file presence and SHA-256 checksums.

Once the process is completed, a full SIP will be available as a folder under the name `[SIPname]_SIP`.

5. Final checks and deposit

- Validate the ingest report (in the documentation folder of the SIP): no missing files or checksum errors.
- Ensure all XML files are schema-valid.
- Review the final SIP structure.
- Compress the SIP **and** the Source Folder as ZIPs and transfer them both securely to the designated archive depository.

6. Cleaning up

Once the SIP has been validated and successfully deposited, clean up temporary files to keep your workspace organized. Mandatory deletions:

- The Source Folder and SIP.
- The Description Form.
- Temporary files such as FilesList.csv, NonCompliantFilesList.csv, and [SIPname]_fits_global.xml.